

1. Diagrammatic representation of a cross section of the rice plant, the insect head, and YAG laser beam focused on proboscis for stylectomy.

2. Diagrammatic representation of a longitudinal section of the rice plant, the insect mouthparts showing the proboscis, the stylets, and the laser beam spot. The stylets reach the sieve tube.

severed the stylet bundle without injuring the semitransparent stylet sheath (which did not absorb the beam). Phloem sap exuded from the cut end of stylets embedded in the phloem sieve element. The electronic measurement of insect feeding behavior (EMIF) improved by Kawabe and McLean in 1980 was useful for determining the tissue in which the

stylets were located at the moment of amputation.

Severed stylets of *N. lugens* were more firmly fixed and provided more phloem sap than that of *N. cincticeps*. Turgor pressure in the sieve element often forced out the stylets of *N. cincticeps*.

The senior author is currently collecting the phloem sap of resistant

and susceptible rice plants through the cut stylets of *N. lugens* to determine the chemical bases of resistance. Besides its use in entomological studies, stylectomy with the YAG laser would help plant pathologists studying disease transmission by sucking insects. ■

Effectiveness and economics of granular insecticides for control of hispa

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The effectiveness of five granular insecticides – quinalphos 5G,

thiodemeton 5G, carbofuran 3G, phorate 10G, and disulfoton 5G – for control of hispa *Dicladispa armigera* (Oliv.) was assessed in the 1978 wet-season rice crop at Jabalpur. The factors measured were population of adult hispa beetles, percentage of leaf damage, and height and length of tillers. The adult

beetle population was assessed by visual counts of 10 random hills in each plot. Net profit was determined by subtracting the cost of insecticide application from the income from increased yield at \$136.47/t.

The granules were applied to Ratna in standing water at 1.5 kg a.i./ha 38 days

Relative performance of some granular insecticides against adults of *D. armigera*, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, India, 1978.^a

Treatment	Adult population (av no./10 hills)				Damaged leaves (%)				Yield (t/ha)	Cost of insecticidal application (\$/ha)	Net profit (\$/ha)
	Pre-treatment	Post-treatment			Pre-treatment	Post-treatment					
		10 days	20 days	30 days		10 days	20 days	30 days			
Quinalphos	3.8 (1.9)	7.5 (2.8)	1.3 (1.2)	0.0 (0.7)	15.2 (22.8)*	19.9 (26.1)*	6.5 (13.9)*	3.1 (9.6)*	2.0	70.89	19.49
Thiodemeton	4.0 (2.3)	2.5 (1.6)	0.0 (0.7)	0.0 (0.7)	16.0 (23.4)*	9.0 (17.3)*	4.9 (12.5)*	1.1 (5.0)*	2.2	50.43	56.02
Carbofuran	3.0 (1.8)	0.0 (0.7)	0.0 (0.7)	0.0 (0.7)	13.7 (21.7)*	5.8 (13.2)*	1.6 (6.2)*	0.2 (1.7)*	2.3	74.97	45.12
Phorate	5.3 (2.3)	3.0 (1.8)	0.8 (1.1)	0.0 (0.7)	17.9 (25.0)*	8.3 (16.4)*	4.2 (11.4)*	2.4 (8.9)*	2.0	43.09	35.41
Disulfoton	3.8 (1.9)	0.0 (0.7)	0.3 (0.8)	0.0 (0.7)	10.3 (18.5)*	8.5 (16.5)*	4.0 (10.9)*	1.8 (7.6)*	1.9	54.66	18.24
Control	3.0 (1.6)	7.0 (2.7)	26.3 (5.1)	20.5 (4.4)	17.4 (24.4)*	48.6 (44.6)*	67.5 (56.7)*	82.0 (71.2)*	1.4	0.00	0.00
S.Em.	0.394	0.211	0.213	0.272	1.66	3.80	4.15	4.81	0.13	–	–
C.D. at 5% level	N.S.	0.640	0.640	0.820	N.S.	11.44	12.50	14.51	0.40	–	–

^a () = $\sqrt{x + 0.05}$; ()* = mean of percentages transformed to angle; N.S. = not significant.

after transplanting – just as adult beetles were migrating from adjacent heavily infested fields and beginning to infest the crop.

Carbofuran-treated plots had no *D.*

armigera population throughout the 30-day experimental period (see table) and yielded the highest (2.3 t/ha), although the insecticidal treatments did not give statistically different yields. The

minimum number of damaged leaves was found in the carbofuran treatment, but treatments again did not differ significantly. Thiodemeton gave the highest net profit (\$56.02/ha). ■

Influence of ammonium phosphate levels on rice leaf roller incidence

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The rice leaf roller *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée (Lepidoptera; Pyralidae) seriously damaged rice plants in a fertilizer experimental plot at Ubon Rice Experiment Station, Rice Fertilizer Branch (Rice Division), in northeastern Thailand during the 1979 wet season. The experiment was in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications and 14 ammonium phosphate (16-20-0) levels. Twenty-eight-day-old seedlings of RD2 rice were transplanted in 3- x 5-m plots. Half the fertilizer with 37.5 kg K₂O/ha was basally applied and the rest was applied 30 days after transplanting.

Effect of nitrogen fertilizer levels on rice leaf folder damage, Ubon Rice Experiment Station, Thailand, 1979.

Nitrogen treatment (kg/ha)	Damaged leaves ^a 52 DT (%)
0	5.4 a
15	9.4 ab
30	10.2 ab
45	14.1 abc
60	12.8 abc
75	22.9 bcd
90	26.5 cd
105	33.2 d
120	34.3 d
135	33.1 d
150	52.8 e
165	62.2 e
180	56.9 e
195	64.2 e
C.V. = 37.0%	

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level (LSD). DT = days after transplanting.

The leaves damaged by the leaf roller and those undamaged on 30 hills randomly selected from each plot were counted.

The result showed that the percentages of damaged leaves rose proportionally with increasing nitrogen levels from 0 to 195 kg N/ha (see table). At 0 nitrogen the damaged leaves were only 5.34% while at 195 kg N/ha the damage was greatest (64.2%). The percentage of damaged leaves sharply increased at 75 kg N/ha level and was significantly different from that in the untreated control treatment.

Increased outbreaks of the rice leaf roller and other rice insects in recent years were believed related to increased use of nitrogenous fertilizer among farmers. How nitrogenous fertilizer affects the insect is not known. It has been reported the insect would oviposit more on dark-green rice plants than on greenish or yellow ones. ■

Soil and crop management

Effect of liming on the control of green algae in blue-green algae multiplication fields

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Green alga (GA) is a problem in paddy fields because it chokes the crop in initial stages, retarding tillering and removing considerable quantities of applied nitrogen. GA are becoming a problem in fields where blue-green algae (BGA) are multiplied. GA appear earlier and grow more luxuriantly in red or sandy soils than in clay soils. Lime, which is commonly used to control GA, was tested for algae control in BGA multiplication units.

Superphosphate fertilizer was applied

at 50 g/m². For pest control 25 g of carbofuran 3% G was applied to each plot. Water was maintained continuously at 5 cm. The field was rich in BGA

inoculum, so no fresh seed material was applied. Lime was applied at 1,250 - 10,000 kg/ha with graded increases of 1,250/kg. The BGA yield was measured

Yield of blue-green algae (BGA) and information on it and on green algae (GA). Aduthurai, India.

Levels of lime (kg/ha)	BGA yield (kg/m ²)	Appearance of GA (days after experiment initiation)	Types ^a of RGA in descending order of abundance
1,250	0.64	23	Ao, Ad, M1, Cm, Afu
2,500	0.52	21	Ao, Cm, M1, Ad, Afu
3,750	0.42	18	Ao, Ad, M1, Cm
5,000	0.29	16	Ao, Ad, M1
6,250	0.16	13	M1, Ao, Ad
7,500	0.10	10	M1, Ao
8,750	0.07	9	M1
10,000	0.05	9	M1
Control	0.17	28	Ao, Ad, M1, Afu
CD	0.055		

^aAd = *Anabaena doliolum*, Afu = *Anabaena fuelleborni*, Ao = *Anabaena oscillarioides*, Cm = *Cylindropermum muscicola*, M1 = *Microcoleus lacustris*.